

REINFORCEMENT LEARNING MODELS FOR ACQUIRING EMOTIONAL MUSICAL MODES

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ABSTRACT

Music is deeply related to emotions. The relationships between musical modes and emotions are especially strong. This has been recognized since the age of ancient Greece. However, finding a mode that represents a specific emotion well by psychological experiments is not easy because there are so many modes mathematically. To deal with this problem, we propose a method to generate modes that represent emotions with an engineering approach that uses reinforcement learning rather than a psychological approach. Since this method gradually adapts a mode to a target emotion, we can expect to obtain a desirable mode without enumerating all the possible modes one by one. However, this method needs a human evaluator who trains the mode. In consideration of reducing the burden on the evaluator, we have designed four function approximation models of the action-value function. As a result of a pilot experiment, the best model could acquire modes that represent “high” representational power of happiness, sadness and tenderness and “a little high” representational power of fear. Additionally, we propose a musicological concept “interval scale” that is derived from the second model and show a possibility of applying it to compose music.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are strong relationships between musical modes and emotions. If we think of bright major mode and dark minor mode, then this is obvious. These relationships have been recognized since the age of ancient Greece. In Plato’s *The Republic* [1], Socrates argues, from an educational viewpoint, that “sad” Lydian mode and “loose” Ionian mode should not be used and that only Dorian and Phrygian modes, which represent “courage” and “moderation” respectively, should be used.¹ Aristotle argues in *Politics* [2] that “aggressive” modes and “enthusiastic” modes can be used in some cases, though Dorian is the most suitable mode for educational purpose because it is the most “calm” and “masculine” mode.

¹ Greek modes mentioned here are different from church modes, though the names are identical.

In recent decades, empirical research of finding correspondence between modes and emotions has been conducted. Kastner et al. [3] performed an experiment about major and minor modes that used illustrations of facial expressions as emotion labels for children. All of the 38 subjects between the age of three and 12 could perceive positive emotion from major mode and negative emotion from minor mode. Hill et al. [4] conducted an experiment in which the subjects listen to Bach’s melodies that consist of Ionian or Phrygian modes and judge which of the modes correspond to “salvation” or “condemnation.” The results shows that Ionian mode corresponds to salvation and Phrygian mode corresponds to condemnation. Ramos et al. [5] mapped seven church modes to the two-dimensional plane of valence and arousal and analyzed the differences of emotions represented by respective church modes. Thompson et al. [6] also found that atonality and chromatic harmony are related to “anger.” In India, there are many types of mode called “raga,” and it is said that Indian musicians can generate various moods by selecting ragas [7].²

A significant difficulty in studying the correspondence between modes and emotions is that there are a very large number of modes mathematically, though we can only investigate a small number of modes practically. Calculated simply, the number of modes (as pitch class sets) in n -tone tuning is 2^n (4096 in 12-tone). Individual investigation is needed for each tuning. Because of this difficulty, most research only treats major and minor modes. Even the research that treats seven church modes like [5] would be approved as highly motivated work. Moreover, if we try to deal with not only mere pitch class sets, but also modes that include tendencies of melodic behavior, the number of modes increases further.

To avoid this difficulty, we propose a new method based on an engineering approach that uses reinforcement learning [9] rather than a psychological approach. In the approach, a mode gradually changes to adapt to a target emotion by feedback given by a human evaluator. It is expected that this method will enable us to obtain desirable modes that represent target emotions well without investigating a very large number of fixed modes. Another possible advantage of this method is that it may be adaptable to individual, cultural, and educational differences.

² Raga is not just a scale. It contains melodic behavior and is regarded as a kind of mode [8]. We use the term mode as a pitch class set that contains tendencies of melodic behavior.

There are some previous studies about application of reinforcement learning in music. They include the research [10] in which a musical agent adapts its parameters to the degree of musical tension desired by a human evaluator. The research [11] that intends to imitate polyphonic musical styles by reinforcement learning from musical scores is also included in such studies. As far as we know, our research is the first attempt to adapt modes to emotions using reinforcement learning.

The outline of this paper is as follows: Section 2 explains the basic methods of reinforcement learning. Section 3 presents our method of learning modes using reinforcement learning, and four function approximation models are introduced. Section 4 reports the results of pilot experiment that evaluates and compares the performances of the four models. Section 5 provides additional remark and proposes a musicological concept “interval scale” that is derived from the second model. Section 6 summarizes this paper.

2. REINFORCEMENT LEARNING

2.1 Basic Framework

Reinforcement learning is an unsupervised machine learning techniques in which an *agent* in an *environment* learns optimal actions through trial and error. The environment repeats state transitions within the state space S at each time step t . The agent observes the *state* $s \in S$ of the environment and takes an *action* $a \in A(s)$, where $A(s)$ is the set of actions available in the state s . Partly as a consequence of its action, the agent receives a *reward* r from the environment. The aim of the agent is to maximize the *return* R_t defined as:

$$R_t = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k r_{t+k+1}, \quad (1)$$

where γ is a parameter, $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$, called the *discount rate*. As γ approaches to 1, the agent takes future rewards into account more strongly.

Using the received reward r as a clue, the agent estimates the value of s , which is denoted by $V(s)$, and the value of the action a at s , which is denoted by $Q(s, a)$. $V(s)$ is called the *state-value function*, and $Q(s, a)$ is called the *action-value function*. $V(s)$ and $Q(s, a)$ are defined as:

$$V(s) = E\{R_t | s_t = s\}, \quad (2)$$

$$Q(s, a) = E\{R_t | s_t = s, a_t = a\}. \quad (3)$$

In many cases, the environment satisfies the Markov property and is called a *Markov Decision Process* (MDP), and the state and action spaces are finite. In MDP, s moves to the next state s' by transition probability $P_{ss'}^a$ when the agent takes an action a . And then, environment gives the agent the reward r whose expected value is $R_{ss'}^a$. Thus, MDP is characterized by $P_{ss'}^a$ and $R_{ss'}^a$.

On the other hand, the agent has a preference in selecting its actions. The agent in a state s takes an action a by probability $\pi(s, a)$. This π is called the *policy*. The value

of $\pi(s, a)$ is determined by referring to $V(s)$ or $Q(s, a)$, in many cases, and the values of $V(s)$, $Q(s, a)$ and $\pi(s, a)$ are improved as time passes.

If $P_{ss'}^a$ and $R_{ss'}^a$ are known and $\gamma < 1$, $V(s)$ and $Q(s, a)$ can be obtained by solving a simultaneous equation called *Bellman equation* without trial and error. In many cases, however, the environment is unknown, and the agent learns through trial and error under $\pi(s, a)$.

2.2 Bootstrapping and Episode

There are many types of reinforcement learning method in unknown environments. The difference between the methods that update value functions step by step and the methods that update value functions after an *episode* ends is especially important for this study, where an episode means a finite series of states experienced under $\pi(s, a)$. This subsection explains the difference.

The general expressions of improvement of the value functions are the following update rules that make $V(s)$ and $Q(s, a)$ closer to the target R_t :

$$V(s_t) \leftarrow V(s_t) + \alpha[R_t - V(s_t)], \quad (4)$$

$$Q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha[R_t - Q(s_t, a_t)], \quad (5)$$

where α is called a step-size parameter that determine the degree of learning in one step. In general, calculating R_t according to equation 1 in a naive manner would require infinite time and is therefore impossible. To make it possible to learn $V(s)$ in real time, the next equation

$$\begin{aligned} V(s) &= E\{R_t | s_t = s\} \\ &= E\left\{\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k r_{t+k+1} | s_t = s\right\} \\ &= E\left\{r_{t+1} + \gamma \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k r_{t+k+2} | s_t = s\right\} \\ &= E\{r_{t+1} + \gamma V(s_{t+1}) | s_t = s\} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

is used to approximate R_t . For example, *TD(0)*, which is a method that updates $V(s)$ step by step, estimates R_t indirectly from the immediate reward r_{t+1} and $V(s_{t+1})$ by the following update rule:

$$V(s_t) \leftarrow V(s_t) + \alpha[r_{t+1} + \gamma V(s_{t+1}) - V(s_t)]. \quad (7)$$

This type of method that estimate the state values indirectly using the estimated values of other states is called *bootstrapping* method. Similar methods can be taken for $Q(s, a)$, too.

On the other hand, there are some cases where the exact calculation is possible. If the series $\{s_t\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$ is divided into the episodes that end in a finite time, R_t can be determined after reaching the ends of the episodes. In such cases, we can directly update $V(s)$ and $Q(s, a)$ that correspond to the states and actions appearing in the episode using the actual R_t by the update rules (4) and (5). This method is called *Montes Carlo method*.

Bootstrapping methods include *TD-learning*, *Q-learning* and *Sarsa* and the methods whose unit is an episode include Monte Carlo method and *profit sharing*. In this study, we adopt Monte Carlo method.

2.3 Function Approximation, Gradient Descent

To train $Q(s, a)$ about all the pairs of (s, a) , long time and large data are required. Therefore, *generalization* of experience is important. Generalization makes it possible to estimate $Q(s, a)$ of which (s, a) has not been experienced yet to an extent. It is accomplished when $Q(s, a)$ is approximated by a function of a parameter vector $\vec{\theta} = (\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_{n-1})^T$ whose number of the elements n is smaller than the number of combinations of s and a .

A *linear approximation* is one of the simplest in such *function approximations*. It approximates $Q(s, a)$ using a *feature vector* $\vec{\phi}(s, a) = (\phi_0(s, a), \phi_1(s, a), \dots, \phi_{n-1}(s, a))^T$ that corresponds to $\vec{\theta}$, and $Q(s, a)$ is expressed as:

$$Q(s, a) = \vec{\theta}^T \cdot \vec{\phi} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \theta_i \cdot \phi_i(s, a). \quad (8)$$

When $Q(s, a)$ is generalized by $\vec{\theta}$, *gradient descent* is often used to update $\vec{\theta}$. It moves the parameters to the direction that decreases the objective function most steeply to minimize it. In this study, the objective function is the square error of the difference between R_t and $Q(s, a)$. The gradient of the square error is calculated as:

$$\nabla_{\vec{\theta}} [R_t - Q(s, a)]^2 = -2[R_t - Q(s, a)] \nabla_{\vec{\theta}} Q(s, a). \quad (9)$$

From this equation, the update rule is expressed as:

$$\vec{\theta} \leftarrow \vec{\theta} + \alpha [R_t - Q(s, a)] \nabla_{\vec{\theta}} Q(s, a). \quad (10)$$

In the case of the linear approximation (8), the gradient can be easily calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\vec{\theta}} Q(s, a) &= \left(\frac{\partial Q(s, a)}{\partial \theta_0}, \dots, \frac{\partial Q(s, a)}{\partial \theta_{n-1}} \right)^T \\ &= (\phi_0(s, a), \phi_1(s, a), \dots, \phi_{n-1}(s, a))^T \\ &= \vec{\phi}(s, a), \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

then the update rule is expressed as:

$$\vec{\theta} \leftarrow \vec{\theta} + \alpha [R_t - Q(s, a)] \cdot \vec{\phi}(s, a). \quad (12)$$

3. PROPOSED METHOD

3.1 Target

The aim of this study is to obtain a “mode that represents the target emotion E .” We define this concept as follows:

Definition 1.³ Let us consider tone series (ordered list) $e = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_T)$ that is generated from a first order Markov chain M on the state space S , where S is the pitch classes of n equal temperament $\mathbb{Z}_n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$. When e is generated repeatedly from M and a human evaluator evaluates that e represents the target emotion E well on average, we call M a “mode that represents the emotion E ,” and denote M by M_E . This definition makes possible to include the tendencies of melodic movements and distinguish a “mode” from a “scale” that is represented by a mere probability distribution of the pitch classes.

³ For the sake of simplicity, we treat only the equal temperaments (especially that of 12 tone in the experiment).

3.2 Monte Carlo Method

As was mentioned in subsection 2.2, we apply Monte Carlo method to obtain M_E . This subsection explains how to apply it.

The action $a \in A(s)$ ($\forall s \in S, A(s) = \mathbb{Z}_n$) is defined as the melodic interval from the current pitch class s to the next pitch class s' . s' is determined uniquely by s and a ($P_{ss'}^a = 1$), and it equals $(s + a) \bmod n$. Tone series $e = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_T)$ is used as the episode. This e is stochastically generated by $\pi(s, a)$ that is defined later. After each episode finishes, the human evaluator decides the reward r_T . Because the evaluation is for all of the states and actions in e , γ is set as 1. Based on this r_T , $V(s)$ and $Q(s, a)$ whose s and a appear in the episode are updated by the rules (4) and (5).

r_T is an integer between -3 and 3 that corresponds to the degree of how much representational power of the emotion E the tone series e has. The meanings of these values are: 3 (very high), 2 (high), 1 (a little high), 0 (neither high nor low), -1 (a little low), -2 (low), -3 (very low). Under such rewards, the state-value function $V(s)$ reflects the necessity of s to express the emotion E and $Q(s, a)$ reflects the necessity of the melodic movement a from s to s' .

Here, let us consider the meaning of the policy π . $\pi(s, a)$ is equal to $Pr(s'|s)$, the transition probability from s to s' . Therefore, π derives a Markov chain. After the convergence of learning an emotion E and the achievement of a high average score, the Markov chain derived from π becomes M_E , a mode that represents the emotion E .

3.3 Policy

In this study, $\pi(s, a)$ that is used to generate the episodes is defined as follows:

$$\pi(s, a) = \begin{cases} \frac{Q(s, a)}{\sum_{u \in A(s)} \sum_{s.t. 0 < Q(s, u)} Q(s, u)} & \text{if } 0 < Q(s, a) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

By this definition, the transition with the positive action-value $Q(s, a)$ will appear according to the probability proportional to $Q(s, a)$, and transition with the negative action value will not appear at all. This policy is expected to eliminate the transitions that are not necessary to represent the target emotion. However, once $Q(s, a)$ becomes under 0, a stops appearing at s . Therefore, it is necessary to prevent the failure to appreciate $Q(s, a)$ by ill fortune. To prevent it, the initial values of $Q(s, a)$ are set as optimistic values (3.0, for example). Optimistic initial values are also known to encourage broad exploration of the state space and action space [9].

3.4 Function Approximation Models

The domain of $Q(s, a)$ is the direct product of the state space and the action space, and $Q(s, a)$ has n^2 values to learn in this case. Learning all these values is inefficient. In this section, therefore, we build four function approximation models. The performances of these models are compared to each other in the next section.

In these function approximations, a parameter vector $\vec{\theta}$ that is common to four models is introduced under the assumption that the melodic interval a has its own worthiness not depending on the pitch class s . This $\vec{\theta}$ consists of $2n$ parameters. The parameters from θ_0 to θ_{n-1} are used to represent the worthinesses of the pitch classes from 0 to $n-1$ respectively and the parameters from θ_n to θ_{2n-1} are used to represent the worthinesses of the melodic intervals from 0 to $n-1$ respectively.

3.4.1 Model 1: Pitch Class Model

This first model approximates $Q(s, a)$ by disregarding the melodic interval a . Only the parameter for the pitch class s' , which is the state reached after the transition, is taken into account. In the linear approximation (8), the feature vector of this model is expressed as follows:

$$\phi_i(s, a) = \phi_i(s') = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = s' \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

The action-value function of this model is expressed as:

$$Q_1(s, a) = \sum_{i=0}^{2n-1} \theta_i \cdot \phi_i(s, a) = \theta_{s'}. \quad (15)$$

In this model, the Markov chain derived from π doesn't depend on the current state s , and it is degenerated to the probability distribution $Pr(s')$.

3.4.2 Model 2: Melodic Interval Model

In contrast with the first model, the second model approximates $Q(s, a)$ by disregarding s' . Only the parameter for the melodic interval a is taken into account. In the linear approximation (8), the feature vector of this model is expressed as follows:

$$\phi_i(s, a) = \phi_i(a) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = n + a \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

The action-value function of this model is expressed as:

$$Q_2(s, a) = \sum_{i=0}^{2n-1} \theta_i \cdot \phi_i(s, a) = \theta_{n+a} \quad (17)$$

In this model, the Markov chain derived from π doesn't depend on s or s' , and it is degenerated to the probability distribution $Pr(a)$.

3.4.3 Model 3: Additive Model

The third model approximates $Q(s, a)$ by the sum of the parameters for s' and a . In the linear approximation (8), the feature vector of this model is expressed as follows:

$$\phi_i(s, a) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = s' \text{ or } i = n + a \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

The action-value function of this model is expressed as:

$$Q_3(s, a) = \sum_{i=0}^{2n-1} \theta_i \cdot \phi_i(s, a) = \theta_{s'} + \theta_{n+a} \quad (19)$$

3.4.4 Model 4: Multiplicative Sigmoid Model

The fourth model is designed to have a synergetic effect of the parameters for s' and a . The action-value function is approximated by the parameters for both s' and a transformed by the sigmoid function:

$$\sigma(\theta) = \frac{1}{(1 + e^{-\theta})}. \quad (20)$$

The sigmoid function has a pair of horizontal asymptotes. It approaches to 0 as $\theta \rightarrow -\infty$ and approaches to 1 as $\theta \rightarrow \infty$, respectively. Using these properties, the range of $\sigma(\theta)$ can be controlled. The action-value function of this model is expressed as:

$$Q_4(s, a) = 6\sigma(\theta_{s'})\sigma(\theta_{n+a}) - 3. \quad (21)$$

Here, we determined the values of the coefficient and the intercept so that $Q_4(s, a)$ is bounded as $-3 < Q_4(s, a) < 3$. Because the derivative of the sigmoid function is expressed as:

$$\frac{d\sigma(\theta)}{d\theta} = \sigma(\theta)(1 - \sigma(\theta)), \quad (22)$$

the gradient of $Q_4(s, a)$ can be calculated using the following partial derivative:

$$\frac{\partial Q_4(s, a)}{\partial \theta_i} = \begin{cases} 6\sigma(\theta_{s'}) (1 - \sigma(\theta_{s'})) \sigma(\theta_{n+a}) & (i = s') \\ 6\sigma(\theta_{n+a}) (1 - \sigma(\theta_{n+a})) \sigma(\theta_{s'}) & (i = n + a) \\ 0 & (\text{otherwise}). \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

4. PILOT EXPERIMENT

In order to examine whether learning musical mode is possible with the proposed method and compare the performances of four models, the first author (he is studying music at the university) carried out a pilot evaluation experiment as an evaluator. n was set as 12. $V(s)$ is also learned by the update rule (4) to see dominant pitch classes.

4.1 Experimental Conditions

As the target emotions, happiness, sadness, fear, and tenderness were selected by referring to the circumplex model adopted by Juslin et al. (Fig. 1 [12]). In this model, many categories of emotions are arranged on a two dimensional plane of valence and arousal. The four emotions are the representatives of the respective quadrants of the two dimensional plane.

The tone series e used as the episode was set up as follows: T was set up as a small number, 5, because there is a fear that learning does not progress speedily if the length of a tone series T is too long. Tonic was set as C (MIDI number 60) and the note at the beginning of the episode was fixed as the tonic. This is because there is a fear that the learning does not progress due to a confusion of keys.

Figure 1. Circumplex model of emotion categories.

In order to evaluate the episodes accurately, each episode was repeated until the evaluator was able to become confident of the evaluation. When the evaluator felt that the learning reached a deadlock, the learning was ended. We adopted this deadlock as the definition of the convergence. twelve pitch classes were represented by the MIDI numbers from 60 to 71. The step-size parameter α was set as 0.1. The durations of the notes were fixed as 300ms, and the timbre of the piano (MIDI) was used.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Reward Transition

The learning processes about the respective emotions by the four models are shown in Fig. 2. The mean rewards of the latest 10 episodes are shown by the lines. We can observe that there are tendencies of convergence toward higher mean rewards than 0 by around the 150th episode. This shows the success of the proposed method to a certain degree. However, the melodic interval model receives smaller rewards (between 0 and 1, in many cases) than other models. This probably indicates that pitch classes have more important roles in representing the emotions than melodic intervals.

The pitch class model and the multiplicative sigmoid model show comparatively good performances in every emotion. They received “high” mean rewards around 2 except for “fear,” and they received “a little high” mean rewards around 1 in “fear.” The multiplicative sigmoid model dominates the pitch class model in “tenderness.” However, the pitch class model converges earlier than the multiplicative sigmoid model. This might be because the former model uses fewer parameters (the parameters for the states s are virtually not used.).

4.2.2 Acquired Modes

The parameters of $\vec{\theta}$ after training are shown in Fig. 3. From this figure, it is observed that the multiplicative sigmoid model (blue) shares the features of ups and downs of the black pitch class model (from θ_0 to θ_{11}) and the features of the red melodic interval model (from θ_{12} to θ_{23}).

Figure 2. Mean rewards.

While each element of the gradients takes 0 or 1 in other models than the multiplicative sigmoid model, the multiplicative sigmoid model has interdependences between the states and the actions in its gradient. This interdependence may be the reason of the dominance of the multiplicative sigmoid model. However, the shapes of ups and downs from θ_0 to θ_{11} are more clear than those of θ_{12} to θ_{23} . This may also suggest that pitch classes are more important in representing emotions than melodic intervals.

Fig. 4 shows the value function $V(s)$. The set of s whose

Figure 3. $\vec{\theta}$ after training.

Figure 4. $V(s)$ after training.

$V(s)$ is clearly larger than 0 means the aspect of the mode as a “scale,” which consists of only pitch classes. These are represented by the vertical dotted lines (these lines refer to the multiplicative sigmoid model, which has the best performance). We can observe that the mode of happiness is identical to Mixolydian mode (on C). The mode of sadness is a Locrian mode to which the pitch D and G are added. The mode of fear can be interpreted as a mode of sadness to which E and B are added. The mode of tenderness is identical to a subset of Ionian mode (major mode).

In the research [5], music samples of the combinations of three tempi and seven church modes are mapped to the two-dimensional plane of valence and arousal. Although it is not easy to interpret the results of the research because of the difference of tempo, the results can be interpreted, at least, that Mixolydian mode and Ionian mode have high arousal, and the Locrian mode has low arousal. This is consistent with the results of our experiment that the mode of happiness, which is considered to have high arousal, was Mixolydian mode and the mode of sadness, which is con-

Figure 5. Japanese traditional modes (ascending and descending forms are merged) [8]. Yosenpou (bright mode) is embedded in the mode of happiness and insenpou (dark mode) is embedded in the mode of sadness. The pitch class sets of the modes of happiness and sadness are represented by the vertical dotted lines.

sidered to have low arousal, was similar to Locrian mode. However, our result that the mode of tenderness was similar to Ionian mode appears to be inconsistent with the result of the research. Considering that the mode of tenderness was a subset of Ionian mode and not the exact Ionian mode, a hypothesis that not using all of the pitch classes of Ionian mode was effective to lower the arousal and to represent tenderness can be suggested. Also from the modes acquired by our experiment, we can make hypotheses that the number of pitch classes is correlated with the height of the arousal and that the number of pitch classes is inversely correlated with the height of the valence. Further investigation of such relations between the constitutions of pitch classes and the types of emotions is an future subject.

Interestingly, a pair of traditional Japanese modes, “yosenpou” and “insenpou,” are embedded in the modes of happiness and sadness, respectively. “Yosenpou” means “bright mode” and “insenpou” means “dark mode” in Japanese. These modes are shown in Fig. 5. These results may suggest that the fact that the evaluator was Japanese affected the results and that there is a consistency between the culture and the results of the training due to the adaptive method. It will be also valuable to investigate personal, cultural, and educational differences by a larger scale experiment in the future.

5. ADDITIONAL REMARK

Although the experiment in the previous section indicates that the second melodic interval model is inferior to the other models, it works to some extent. Moreover, it is musically very important. In this section, we present the concept “interval scale” derived from the second model and show that the concept can be an alternative basis of music composition (especially in atonal music).

The concept “scale” usually just means a constitution of pitch classes, and the constitution of melodic intervals is of second importance in many cases. However, we define “interval scale” as a concept that reversed it. That is to say, “interval scale” just means a set of melodic intervals, and the constitution of pitch classes is not restricted. “Interval scale” is exactly the object to which we tried to obtain by using the second model. To distinguish “interval scale” with usual scale, we call an usual scale a “pitch scale.”

Figure 6. The opening of Ligeti’s Étude No. 2.

It is obvious that a musical piece based on a pitch scale exists. However, is there a musical piece based on some interval scales? Ligeti’s piano piece “Étude No. 2: Cordes à vide” may be an good example. The title means “open string.” As is guessed from it, ascending and descending perfect fifths (intervals of 5 and 7) are used all over the piece. Fig. 6 shows the opening of this piece.

The collection of all the melodic intervals between adjacent eighth notes in Fig. 6 is $\{5, 6, 7, 8\}$. The number of the elements of this set is small, and there is a feature that the elements are consecutive numbers. The interval 6 and 8 are adjacent to 5 and 7 respectively, and 6 and 8 make it possible to transpose the motions of perfect fifths mildly and play a role of preventing fixation of the melodies.

On the other hand, the pitch scale of this part of the piece includes all the pitch classes, and it is, therefore, chromatic scale. When a piece is based on an interval scale, it is not accidental that a pitch scale becomes the chromatic scale. That is because the interval 7, for example, can generate all the pitch classes passing through the circle of fifths. Conversely, even if a piece of music is atonal music, it is conceivable that an characteristic interval scale is implicitly used in the piece. The Ligeti’s piece shows that interval scale can be used as a basis of composing atonal music.

To characterize interval scale from the standpoint of emotion, we define the following pair of concepts that are related to the first and the second models.

Definition 2. After the reinforcement learning of the emotion E by the first model has converged on a mean reward larger than 0, we call $\{s \in \mathbb{Z}_n | \theta_s > \epsilon\}$ “a pitch scale that represents the emotion E ,” where ϵ is an adequate threshold.

Definition 3. After the reinforcement learning of the emotion E by the second model has converged on a mean reward larger than 0, we call $\{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n | \theta_{a+n} > \epsilon\}$ “an interval scale that represents the emotion E ,” where ϵ is an adequate threshold.

By these definitions and the results of the experiment, Mixolydian mode, for example, is a pitch scale that represents happiness and the interval set $\{2, 3, 5, 7, 10\}$ is an interval scale that represents happiness. Although finding an existing music piece based on specific interval scales will be difficult, the proposed method may be useful to select appropriate interval scales for emotional expressions in composing music from now on. What is important is that interval scales may be useful to express emotions even

in atonal music.

In reinforcement learning, by the way, the state-value function $V(s)$, which disregards the action a , and the action-value function $Q(s, a)$, which depends on both s and a , are used. However, why is the following action-value function $W(a)$, which disregards s , not used?:

$$W(a) = E\{R_t | a_t = a\}. \quad (24)$$

This is probably because, in most of the problems of reinforcement learning, reaching the goal states is treated as the purpose and the actions are regarded as interchangeable with other alternative actions. This bias that gives priority to the states rather than the actions may have something to do with the fact that interval scale has not been focused on in music. However, when the actions themselves are also important like in music, the value function like $W(a)$ may become important. θ_{n+a} in the proposed method corresponds to such values of a independent of s .

6. CONCLUSION

We proposed a method to obtain modes that represent target emotions based on reinforcement learning, and four function approximation models were proposed and compared to each other. As a consequence of the pilot experiment of learning four categories of emotions, the multiplicative sigmoid model, which was the best model in the four models, could generate the modes that have high representational power of happiness, sadness and tenderness and the mode that has a little high representational power of fear. From comparison of the models, it was suggested that pitch classes are more important for representing the emotions than melodic intervals. The mode of happiness was identical to Mixolydian mode and it consists of 7 pitch classes. Japanese yousenpou was embedded in it. The mode of sadness was a Locrian mode to which the pitch D and G are added and it consists of 9 pitch classes. Japanese insenpou was also embedded in it. The mode of fear was a mode of 11 pitch classes without the pitch class 9. The mode of tenderness was a subset of Ionian mode and it consists of 6 pitch classes. From these, we hypothesized that the number of pitch classes is correlated with the height of the arousal and inversely correlated with the height of the valence. However, further experiments are needed to confirm these hypotheses. Additionally, we presented the concept "interval scale," which was derived from the second function approximation model, and the possibility of applying it to compose atonal music was suggested.

The following issues are included in the future subjects:

- Further investigation of the proposed method in more categories of emotions.
- Application of the proposed method to other tunings such as microtonal tunings and non-octave tunings.
- Investigation of personal, cultural, educational influences.
- Expansion of the proposed method to other musical elements such as timbre, register, tempo, rhythm, and chord.

- Mathematical and musicological investigations about the property of interval scales and application of the concept to compose music.

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